

SPOTTING ONLINE BULLYING BEHAVIOR

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ABSTRACT: Social media is a breeding ground for bullying among young people, with cyberbullying on the rise alongside the increasing popularity of social networking sites. In response to this trend, leveraging machine learning techniques becomes crucial for identifying and addressing instances of bullying. While numerous methods for detecting social media bullying have been proposed, many of them have relied solely on textual analysis. Our project endeavors to showcase how the combination of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) can effectively identify bullying across different mediums like tweets and posts. Our approach involves the utilization of NLP for analyzing the content of textual comments, while CNN is employed for identifying bullying in images. By integrating both NLP and CNN classifiers, we achieve higher accuracy in identifying instances of bullying. Furthermore, we utilize the Twitter API to retrieve tweets, which are then fed into our model to determine whether they contain instances of bullying. This holistic method not only improves the precision of identifying bullying but also aids in preventing such conduct on Twitter and analogous platforms.

Keywords: CNN(Convolution Neural Networks), SVM(Support Vector Machine), NLP (Natural Language Processing), Pre-processing, Feature Extraction, Segmentation.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advancement of technology, the internet has evolved into a secure avenue for communication, although social media platforms remain vulnerable to cybercrimes. Cyberbullying, characterized by the use of online communication to intimidate or threaten individuals, is widespread, with around 87 percent of today's youth having encountered some form of it. Cyberbullying takes on diverse forms such as sexual harassment, the creation of hostile environments, seeking revenge, or retaliating against others.

The anonymity of perpetrators adds complexity to the issue of cyberbullying. With the widespread use of social media and the internet, instances of cyberbullying have increased significantly, making detection a challenge. Hence, it is essential to recognize and address cyberbullying to protect adolescents. Textual cyberbullying detection has garnered considerable attention in the realm of computer science, leading to the development of automated surveillance systems to combat it.

This research utilizes crucial data and textual information to improve the effectiveness of existing cyberbullying detection methods. A pivotal tool in this effort is the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), also known as ConvNet. CNNs represent a specific type of artificial neural network that employs perceptrons, a machine learning algorithm, to analyze data. They are utilized not only in image processing but also in natural language processing and various cognitive tasks.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. **Evaluation of Machine Learning Algorithms :** The authors of this paper conducted a thorough assessment of twelve machine learning algorithms to detect abnormal behaviors signaling potential cyber attacks. They evaluated these algorithms using three datasets: UNSW-NB15, CICIDS-2017, and ICS cyberattack. However, deep learning classification demands substantial data for training models, which wasn't available in the present studies. Among the evaluated methods, Naive Bayes classification exhibited the poorest performance in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and AUC.
2. **The Role of Artificial Intelligence and Cyber Security for Social Media:** This paper has discussed the benefits of social media and the application of machine learning techniques for social media. For example, machine learning techniques are being used to detect the sentiment of the users and to provide information on the spread of deadly diseases as well as prevent child trafficking. It also discussed the use of machine learning for detecting fake news and malicious software. Next, the paper discussed security and privacy issues for social media systems including access control models and privacy aware social media systems. Finally, the paper discussed the integration of AI ad cyber security for social media systems such as adversarial machine learning and the inference and privacy problems.
3. **A Framework to Predict Social Crime through Twitter Tweets By Using Machine Learning:** The objective of this research is to anticipate social media crimes through the analysis of Twitter data. Three machine learning classifiers are employed alongside a bag-of-words model, demonstrating improved performance compared to current methodologies. The proposed model, currently in an offline state, is slated for future extension to enable real-time prediction of Twitter-based crimes. Enhancements may include the addition of additional crime categories to bolster system effectiveness and resilience, though image detection is not within the scope of this endeavor.
4. **Identifying Cyberbullying on Twitter Through Machine Learning:** An approach is proposed for detecting and preventing Twitter cyber bullying using Supervised Binary classification Machine Learning algorithms. This model is evaluated on both Support Vector Machine(SVM) and Naive Bayes, also for feature extraction, used the TFIDF vectorizer. As the results shows that the accuracy for detecting cyber bullying content has also been great for Support Vector Machine which is better than Naive Bayes. But this technique doesn't identify bullying text more accurately.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

1. **Data Collection:** Gather a diverse and comprehensive dataset consisting of text, images, and videos obtained from various online platforms like social media, forums, and messaging apps. Make sure this dataset includes labeled examples of both cyberbullying and non-cyberbullying content.
2. **Data Preprocessing:** Prepare the dataset by cleaning, preprocessing, and annotating it to ensure uniformity, readying it for training the deep learning models. This involves tasks like text tokenization, resizing images, and extracting video frames.

3. **Model Architecture:** Create and deploy a hybrid deep learning architecture merging LSTM and CNN layers. LSTM layers will be tasked with analyzing textual data, while CNN layers will specialize in processing image and video content. Refine the architecture to enhance performance.
4. **Feature Extraction:** Identify pertinent characteristics within text, images, and videos that encompass the linguistic, visual, and contextual indicators linked to cyberbullying.
5. **Training and Validation:** Train the model utilizing the preprocessed dataset and employ cross-validation techniques to ensure its robustness while minimizing overfitting.
6. **Real-time Detection:** Design an interface or API enabling users to submit text, images, or videos for instant detection of cyberbullying. The system must promptly deliver feedback regarding the probability of cyberbullying occurrence and the severity of the submitted content.
7. **Model Evaluation:** Assess the effectiveness of the LSTM-CNN model by employing suitable metrics like precision, recall, F1-score, and accuracy. Contrast the outcomes with those obtained from established cyberbullying detection techniques.
8. **User Alerts and Reporting:** Develop a system to alert users or moderators upon the detection of cyberbullying content. Incorporate features for reporting and logging to facilitate subsequent analysis and intervention.

IV. DATASETS

```
File Edit Selection View Go Run Terminal Help
cyberbullying_lstm.ipynb cyberbullying_lstm.ipynb (output) X
1 | yeah I got 2 backups for all that. I just hate...
2 | I hate using my BB but love my iPhone. Haven'...
3 | Get fucking real dude.
4 | She is as dirty as they come and that crook ...
5 | why did you fuck it up. I could do it all day...
6 | Dude they dont finish enclosing the fucking s...
7 | WTF are you talking about Men? No men thats n...
8 | Ill save you the trouble sister. Here comes a ...
9 | Im dead serious.Real athletes never cheat don...
10 | wow lol sounds like a lot of piss then hehehe
11 | not a damn thang..the typical rap beef. one pe...
12 | ...go absolutely insane.hate to be the bearer ...
13 | well damn!! where have you been when i have ne...
14 | watching without a trace too..hate when i mis...
15 | which they do most of the time:P I don't hate...
16 | Lmao im watching the same thing ahaah. The ga...
17 | LOL no he said What do you call a jail cell ...
18 | truth on both counts that guy is an ass and t...
19 | shakespeare need!
20 | you are SUCH a fucking dork
21 | Heh. Fuck 'em WHERE?!?
22 | damn it i totally forgot that one!
23 | haha fuck i wish i was there :(
24 | paranoid is wack as fuck..the best song on 80...
25 | wow damn I would have been pissed @ that...
26 | nigga u geigh lmao! fuck yo finals beeeeeeitch
27 | in London I hate thee :( ENJOY YOURSELVES!!! ...
28 | lolipop lolipop...oh loli loli loli...duh du...
29 | that sucks :(
30 | read that this morning, my fav is how they jus...
31 | ...
32 | 8787 who'd you piss off? oh...wait...that's a ridic...
33 | 8788 man they photoshopped the fuck out of summer ...
34 | 8789 I'm not feeling emo. I'm more in a relentless...
35 | 8790 I've tried giving you treats wet food milk. ...
36 | 8791 damn. i tried to talk peeps into venturing els...
37 | 8792 I agree. There are a lot of pregnant women and...
38 | 8793 I hadn't really known a lot about her until I ...
39 | 8794 Thanks coke whore!
40 | 8795 Because you're a coke whore maybe?
41 | 8796 damn... U should just stay home and call it a ...
42 | 8797 oh my god... XD sucks for you Talei
43 | 8798 yeah yeah. I've seen your dart board with thei...
44 | 8799 It sucks but at least my car wasn't stolen. ri...
45 | 8800 It may even suck ass.
46 | 8801 Ah. Gay!
47 | 8802 I hate you so much I just want to smash your f...
48 | 8803 Yes you are a loser... I could have told you t...
49 | 8804 just because of a dang song. Over it now but d...
50 | 8805 I dunno I hate it though. Someone at work ga...
51 | 8806 I've made myself achingly sore playing mario a...
52 | 8807 I like shopping I hate lines. My therapist as...
53 | 8808 been there done that it really sucks. One of ...
54 | 8809 Dude I've given up. After a girl who didn't w...
55 | 8810 he doesnt know i know hes gay or bi or w.e. He...
56 | 8811 its not just that corinne is a bitch she's pr...
57 | 8812 no caffiene would kick my ass too - I'm addict...
58 | 8813 Now I'm hungry. Damn you people and your midn...
59 | 8814 i've taken one also. people just piss me off m...
60 | 8815 That too! Or even being able to park pulling ...
61 | 8816 . . . HE'S FUCKING HIMSELF!
62 | Name: text_message, Length: 8817, dtype: object
```

FIG 1

```
File Edit Selection View Go Run Terminal Help
cyberbullying_lstm.ipynb cyberbullying_lstm.ipynb (output) X
27 | in London I hate thee :( ENJOY YOURSELVES!!! ...
28 | lolipop lolipop...oh loli loli loli...duh du...
29 | that sucks :(
30 | read that this morning, my fav is how they jus...
31 | ...
32 | 8787 who'd you piss off? oh...wait...that's a ridic...
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60 | 8815 That too! Or even being able to park pulling ...
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```

FIG 2

V. METHODOLOGY

Fig 5: DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

1. Basic CNN Architecture:

- Artificial intelligence has experienced a notable enhancement in its capacity to connect humans and machines, greatly shaped by image recognition and processing. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), a specific type of neural network, mimic the interconnected neurons in the human visual cortex. These networks, by scanning photos using adjustable weights and dimensions, play a pivotal role in the advanced diagnosis and treatment of numerous diseases. COVnets, an abbreviation for convolutional neural networks, represent another variant of this neural network architecture. The capacity of artificial intelligence to bridge the gap between people and machines has notably increased.
- Image recognition and image processing play a significant role in shaping artificial intelligence.
- Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), a type of neural network, analyze images using adjustable weights and sizes, inspired by the neural connections in the human visual cortex.
- COVnets, also known as convolutional neural networks, constitute a specific category of neural networks.
- The core of the process hinges on CNN layers employed for processing, with key layers including the Sequential Layer.
- Keras' foundational unit is a model, with the simplest being the sequential model, comprised of stacked neural network layers.
- The network is dense, implying that every node from each layer connects with nodes from other layers.
- A perceptron, a single algorithm, takes an input vector x with m values and yields either 1 (yes) or 0 (no).
- The sigmoid function, expressed as $1 / (1 + e^{-x})$, can generate continuous values.
- ReLu, an activation function, produces smooth outputs with nonlinear properties, defined as $f(x) = \max(0, x)$, where the function is 0 for negative values and increases for positive values..

2. Natural Language Processing:

- Natural language processing (NLP) is a subset of machine learning, which itself is part of the broader field of artificial intelligence (AI).
- NLP integrates AI and computational linguistics to facilitate seamless communication between computers and humans.
- The primary goal of NLP is to enable computers to understand and interpret user input, a task that poses significant challenges.
- NLP serves as a tool for computers to intelligently analyze, comprehend, and extract meaning from natural language.
- NLP comprises two fundamental components: Natural Language Understanding and Natural Language Generation.

VI. RESULTS

BEFORE BUILDING MODEL:

AFTER BUILDING MODEL:

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

- Internet crimes pose significant danger due to the continuous targeting of victims, leaving little chance for escape. Among these crimes, cyberbullying stands out as particularly severe, with research illustrating its detrimental effects on victims.
- Utilizing an accurate CNN implementation through Keras, our system ensures precise outcomes, thereby aiding users in avoiding the harsh consequences of cyberbullying.
- Therefore, in comparison to existing models, our technique promises to yield more accurate results in identifying instances of cyberbullying.

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